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LEGAL EDUCATION IS THE BASIS OF LEGAL CULTURE

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Abstract. The main logical steps in the formation of the legal culture of society, the place and role of legal education in it are considered. The process of creating legal values is of an objective nature and is associated with the manifestation of the essential and natural in law. Legal science and legal education act in this process as attributive elements of the spiritual basis of legal culture. It is a prerequisite for the identification, preservation and development of the material elements of legal culture.

Key words: state, law, legal consciousness, legal culture, person, legal education, society, politics.

The importance of legal education for our country is determined by the tasks of transition to a democratic society, a legal state, and a market economy. The new socio-economic conditions significantly increase the traditional problem of education - the most important component of any educational system, the search for ideals that can be the basis of goal setting. The target component of the educational system determines the specific characteristics of the means of achieving these goals, the criteria for evaluating the obtained results, and possible adjustments to the specific direction of the educational process. In the context of modernization of law and legal education, the issue of forming the legal culture, sense of justice, value direction of future lawyers is gaining special importance.

Among the various problems of modern legal education in Uzbekistan, development of the main directions of legal policy in the field of legal education occupies one of the main places. Legal education should be based on the model of a lawyer focused on the needs of the development of society and the achievement of the goals of state-legal development. Due to the fact that such goals have not yet been clearly defined, there is a need to analyze the relationship between legal policy and legal education policy, legal ideology and legal education, legal culture of a lawyer and legal education in modern Uzbekistan.

Accordingly, the problem of studying the professional legal culture of lawyers in connection with the educational effect of legal education arises. This is related to the role of lawyers in ensuring the effective functioning of the legal regulation

mechanism at all stages. Not only the effective functioning of the legal regulatory mechanism, but also the attitude of ordinary citizens to law and legal institutions depends to a large extent on the level of activity of lawyers. In other words, the authority of the law and the state, the level of legal consciousness of the population, and the legal culture are largely determined by the professional skills of the legal staff. However, the most urgent problem of modern legal education is the quality of training of lawyers.

Consequently, the educational and legal aspects of the qualitative renewal of the legal education system, the preparation of students, the acquisition of a certain amount of knowledge and skills mastered in the study of legal sciences, legal knowledge, the style of legal thinking, It also indicates the formation of legal knowledge skills, legal relations, legal culture and skills.

In this way, Uzbekistan is confidently moving towards the establishment of a democratic legal state and the formation of a just civil society, taking a strong place in the world community. Stability and order, inter-ethnic harmony and civil solidarity have earned the young state confidence and respect.

Large-scale reforms in the field of economy, politics, state building, legal system and moral transformation of society have started in the country. The legal framework for the reforms being implemented has been created. The legal foundations of socio-political life are being consistently strengthened and improved.

The progressive movement of society, the success of reforms largely depends on the level of people's legal awareness and legal culture. A person's political activity, his true civic position, and his propensity for democratic reforms are the most important factors in achieving the intended goals [1].

Protecting the rights and interests of individuals and families, further improving the legal culture of the population, and establishing a democratic legal state and civil society in the process of consistent reforms being implemented in the construction of New Uzbekistan under the leadership of President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev is defined as an important task.

The decree of the head of our state dated January 9, 2019 on improving legal education, improving the legal culture of the population, improving the system of training legal personnel, and improving public opinion research is an important program in this regard.

A high legal culture is the basis of a democratic society and an indicator of the maturity of the legal system. It is a factor that actively affects the regulation of various life processes in society, contributes to the unification of citizens and all

social groups, supports and strengthens the integrity of society, order in it. Respect for the law is one of the main requirements for the effective functioning of legal society, political and legal systems.

Legal culture is an integral part of general culture. The belief that only a person who has legal knowledge and knows how to apply it in practice can be considered cultured and educated should be firmly established in the minds of people. The current state of development of the society and the state demands comprehensive improvement of legal culture and legal literacy of all participants of legal relations. Legal culture as a combination of legal knowledge, legal confidence and active practical activity is aimed at ensuring the successful solution of the tasks facing the society and the state.

Based on the need of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure human rights and interests in our country, to create conditions for the democratization of public life and the formation of the foundations of a legal state, and to improve the legal culture in society, accordingly, on January 1, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decree "On fundamental improvement of the system of raising legal consciousness and legal culture in society" was adopted.

The purpose of this Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is for all layers of the population to have legal literacy, to achieve a high level of legal consciousness, to create a comprehensive and permanent system of legal culture formation and to be able to apply legal knowledge in everyday life.

The main tasks to achieve this goal are as follows:

- improvement of the system of legal education and legal culture;
- achieving respect for the law and individual rights by all government bodies, officials and citizens;
- increase the legal literacy of the population;
- to ensure the social and legal activity of citizens.

The state policy in the field of formation and development of legal culture is based on the following principles:

- priority of human rights and freedoms;
- the Constitution and the rule of law;
- democracy;
- social justice;
- scientific character;
- continuity;
- continuity and universality of legal education;

- availability of legal information;
- unified and differentiated approach to legal education and enlightenment.

"...we have done great work on raising the development of the education and training system to a new level. The results of our practical work, the scope and efficiency of which is increasing year by year, can be seen in the successes of our compatriots, especially our dear children, in various fields" [2.405].

In the President's speech "The concept of further deepening of democratic reforms and formation of civil society in our country", it was emphasized that the consistent movement of the society on the path of democracy, the success of democratic reforms depends to a large extent on the level of legal consciousness and legal culture of people. A high legal culture is the basis of a democratic society and an indicator of the maturity of the legal system. In this regard, taking into account the modern political and legal reality, it is important to ensure the creation of a targeted comprehensive program of measures aimed at the fundamental improvement of legal education and enlightenment in our country, and the promotion of legal knowledge in society. The implementation of this program should ensure respect for human rights and freedoms among the population, and the formation of law-abiding behavior of citizens [3.73].

Wide-scale measures are being implemented in our country to improve the legal culture of the population, to increase the scope and effectiveness of legal propaganda.

In educational institutions, community gatherings, and through the mass media, large-scale explanatory work is being carried out to improve the legal knowledge and culture of the population, especially young people, and to strengthen the rule of law. Examinations and interviews were held among students of general education schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges in order to strengthen their knowledge of legal culture, the Constitution and laws. "Round discussions" are organized with the participation of jurists and spiritual promoters on topics such as "Human rights are the highest value", "You know your rights and duties", "My rights".

Legal culture is related to legal consciousness and relies on it, but it is an independent category, because it includes not only socio-psychological processes, which are strengthened in the relevant legal norms, but also legally significant behavior of people, law-making and its results, and legal activity includes.

Legal culture includes elements of public consciousness related to legal institutions and their practice, the formation of certain options of legal behavior of people in society, community.

The components are as follows:

- ✓ legal relations
- ✓ legal conduct
- ✓ legal consciousness
- ✓ creation and operation of legal institutions
- ✓ application of the rule of law.

In addition, the level of the elements of legal culture of states, that is, the "levels of legal development" of the components of the system of legal life of society:

- 1) legal texts (documents and texts with legal content);
- 2) legal activity (theoretical and practical);
- 3) legal consciousness
- 4) subjects of legal culture.

Thus, the importance of legal education in the formation of the legal culture of a student or citizen in the process of legal education increases, but it is still almost neglected. The educational standard does not contain a complete concept of legal education. Creation of a complete foundation of professional education requires additional research with the participation of scientists of law, pedagogy, and psychology. The use of not only extracurricular activities at the university, but also education within the framework of traditional classes is an important factor in successfully solving educational problems. For this purpose, taking into account the fact that legal education is inextricably linked and that legal education is carried out through the acquisition of direct knowledge, teaching within the framework of legal education and it is necessary to develop recommendations on optimal harmonization of education.

The formation of the legal culture of the student is ensured by observing the following set of pedagogical conditions:

- the quality of the surrounding legal environment is created, which serves as a strong decisive factor in the legal education of the subject;
- the structural-functional model of forming the legal culture of the student was developed and implemented; provision of personnel for the educational process at the university, special scientific and methodological training of legal teachers;
- directing the professional education process to the formation of legal culture throughout the entire period of professional training of students;

- organization of interaction between the subject and the subject in the "student-teacher" system;
- continuous improvement of content, forms and methods of legal education and training.

Only in this case, it is possible to form qualities such as positive motivation for the professional activity of a future lawyer, as well as deep respect for the law, values of the rule of law, and others. After all, legal education means treating the law with respect, seeing the law as a great social value that directly concerns every person, forming a sense of responsibility, and not tolerating arbitrariness and corruption.

The strategic task of modern education is to educate a competitive citizen of the world, a spiritually developed person, ready to respond to the demands of the times, brought up on the Russian national soil. In connection with the need to form a legal state, accordingly, in modern conditions, the problem of studying the subjective factor in the field of law and, in particular, the problem of forming the legal culture of an individual as the main characteristic, arises. Today, the legal training of students has proven to be ineffective in ensuring the true professional skills and competence of future professionals. Therefore, it is necessary to qualitatively update the system of legal training of students, which will ensure that they not only acquire a certain amount of knowledge and skills in the study of legal sciences, but also learn the ways of developing legal thinking and legal thinking includes and effective participation in new legal relations, that is, they will have a developed legal culture.

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